

STEAM Classrooms: A Neuroscience-Based Educational Transformation Experience within UNAL's Digital Framework

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Abstract

The National University of Colombia (UNAL) has successfully integrated a STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics) curriculum across its campuses in Manizales, Tumaco, Medellín, and Bogotá to foster inclusivity and reduce student dropout rates. This initiative, spearheaded by the Academic Directorate and supported by the University Laboratory Division, leverages insights from neuroscience and neurodidactics to craft learning experiences that enhance both cognitive and emotional aspects of student learning. The expansion of the STEAM-Fablab classrooms through the Inter-Campus Laboratories Collaboration Network has promoted creativity, co-innovation, and technological development, significantly strengthening digital competencies within the UNAL community. Tailored methodologies address the unique needs of each campus, with specialized training sessions ranging from 3D printing and CNC machining to knowledge management and extended reality. Local adaptations ensure relevance, such as sensor technology for marine system monitoring in Tumaco, sustainability designs in Medellín, and additive manufacturing for artistic development in Bogotá, showcasing a dynamic, interdisciplinary approach to education that prepares students for future challenges.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Neuroeducation; Neurodidactics; STEAM.

1 Introduction

La Universidad Nacional de Colombia (UNAL) is committed to promoting the quality of education in science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics (STEAM). This objective seeks to reduce dropout rates and project education by harmonizing its mission functions: teaching, research, and outreach. Thus, activities that promote the learning of skills and competencies for the present and the digital future are encouraged from training.

Scientific and technological advances have influenced the promoting of these skills and competencies and pedagogical and didactic changes. Thus, evidence-based education is defined as educational information and action based on reports and scientific studies that help us make better decisions in the educational field (Slavin, 2002). Thus, academic actions and decisions are impacted by science.

In this context, neuroscience has emerged as an invaluable tool in education, offering an increasingly deep understanding of how the brain functions during learning, establishing the neural mechanisms underlying cognition, including skills such as attention, memory, creativity, reasoning, and language. As a meeting point for different disciplines, neuroscience provides a scientific foundation for developing more effective and personalized pedagogical strategies. Thus, integrating neuroscientific findings into educational practice optimizes the teaching and learning process and opens new frontiers to address complex educational challenges and promote comprehensive student development. To facilitate understanding in both the public and academia, the term "neuroeducation" has been used.

The goals of STEAM education include promoting STEAM literacy and preparing students for complex changes in the real world (Zollman, 2012). Integrating science, technology, engineering, and mathematics into authentic

contexts can be as complex as the global challenges that demand a new generation of STEAM experts. Teachers need help to establish connections between STEAM disciplines. Consequently, students often show little interest in science and mathematics when they learn in isolation and disjointedly, without connections to cross-cutting concepts and real-world applications. This requires a conceptual framework to guide the actions of teachers and experts designing educational policies and programs (Kelley & Knowles, 2016).

To engage students in STEAM education, it is necessary to foster scientific research, have a rigorous curriculum, and integrate technology into these plans (Kennedy & Odell, 2014).

The Academic Directorate of UN Manizales Campus has been implementing strategies over the past few years for transitioning to spaces involving STEAM teaching-learning methodologies, focusing on the university community, and reaching students from different secondary schools nationwide through various learning outreach programs. The goal is to attract future graduates to pursue careers in this field. Among these strategies is the design and implementation of an academic workspace, managed from a central level of the University, equipped with pedagogical tools for the formulation and execution of projects within the framework of 4.0 technologies. This space (STEM Classroom - Manizales Campus FabLab) was created to support students and the university community in developing interdisciplinary academic activities involving topics from different subjects, where science, technology, engineering, and mathematics can be integrated into learning.

Thus, this study presents a learning methodology implemented by the STEAM classroom. This methodology has as its pillar the student's interaction with the different mental processes carried out in acquiring knowledge, allowing them to be directly involved in research and development of solutions.

Evidence from studies in neuroeducation has found differences between traditional education and education in which STEAM classrooms have been implemented. The main findings are that our brains synchronize in STEAM classrooms (Davidesco, 2020), and students are more sociable (Linton et al., 2014).

Goswami (2018) believes better teacher teaching is required for better student learning. Thus, neuroscience provides tools that contribute to improving educational practices. Below are three proposed principles for this (Blakemore & Frith, 2011). They are firstly, designing more effective and meaningful learning experiences for students. This involves considering the cognitive and emotional processes that occur in the brain during learning. Secondly, connecting concepts with students' previous experiences creates a bridge between the familiar and the new, thus facilitating learning and information retention; and thirdly, promoting collaboration and critical thinking, which contribute to jointly constructing active learning through reflective and objective information analysis processes.

Therefore, in the UNAL STEAM Classrooms, integrated practices are carried out in which explicit connections are made, meaning that students must understand how STEAM knowledge applies to real-world contexts. Additionally, support is provided for them to generate ideas, relate them productively, and reorganize them in a way that develops information reformulation processes, reflecting normative scientific practices. This combines stimulating experiences, critical thinking skills, increased attention spans, and problem-solving.

A learning activity's physical and social contexts are crucial to the learning process. This is where situated learning comes into play. Learning based on a situated context becomes authentic and relevant, representing an experience encountered in actual STEAM practice (Putnam & Borko, 2000). When considering the integration of STEAM content, engineering design can become the situated context and platform for STEAM learning.

Figure 1. STEAM Classroom at the Medellín Campus.

2 Methods

The objective has been to create a collaboration network of inter-campus laboratories to strengthen creativity and digital skills by establishing three immersive STEAM satellite classrooms in the Tumaco, Bogotá, and Medellín campuses. To enrich project-based learning methodology through neurodidactics, methods that activate information processing, reinforcement in working memory, reasoning, questioning, and practicing what has been learned are necessary to make the learning process efficient (Dunlosky et al., 2013).

Through this methodology, the aim is for students to take the lead in their learning journey. They will engage in independent research development, where they can develop skills and knowledge focused on the STEAM field, learn to use cutting-edge equipment, and produce innovative and viable ideas in response to the challenges that arise in their respective environments. In this way, the educational process allows for exploring various disciplines in an integrated manner and develops vital competencies such as critical thinking, collaboration, and effective communication.

2.1 Neurodidactics

Neurodidactics defines *learning* as: "Any variation in synaptic connections that produce changes in thought and behavior. Modifications can occur through theoretical information, practice, or life experiences" (Paz et al., 2018). Neurodidactics responds to the following basic principles, which should be considered in this methodology (Ozden & Gultekin, 2008):

- Motivation in students is essential to achieve their learning.
- To achieve authentic learning, involving students in the processes is necessary.
- Learning requires respect for students' rhythms, interests, states, and needs.
- Learning requires research, meaning-making, reasoning, and understanding.
- Each student's emotions are deterministic factors in learning.
- The role of mirror neurons in learning is undeniable.

This methodology is not just a theoretical concept but a practical tool to make information reach students more effectively. It is designed to steer learning towards each person's meaningful long-term memories, transforming them into lasting knowledge. A study conducted by MIT (Poh et al., 2010) provides concrete evidence: students in a traditional classroom-only partially activate their brain capacity compared to when the teacher involves them in project development, as in the methodology proposed here.

An essential element, according to experts, for learning is motivation. The brain process of motivation is known as DAS, where neurotransmitters such as dopamine, adrenaline, and serotonin are activated (Chávez & Chávez, 2020).

Below is how the methodology proposed in this article intends to cover the brain's motivation process:

Desire: Finding a simple solution to a problem.

Action: Designing and establishing the requirements to have the best solution.

Satisfaction: Applying the solution to the problem posed.

Figure 2. Brain process of motivation.

In summary, this strategy aims to understand and enhance students' skills. Without losing sight of motivation, learning is characterized by being both a cognitive and motivational process simultaneously (Schultz W., 2015).

3 Procedure

3.1 Learning with STEAM Methodologies

By establishing STEAM Classrooms at the Bogotá, Medellín, and Tumaco campuses, we are not just meeting the need for comprehensive learning in science, technology, engineering, art, and mathematics in these communities. We are creating innovative spaces to provide training opportunities and develop technological, creative, and collaborative skills. These spaces will foster innovation and entrepreneurship, generating real solutions to current challenges. Moreover, by integrating environmental themes, we will raise awareness and contribute to environmental conservation, promoting sustainable development in the regions. This initiative can potentially transform these communities, inspiring a brighter future.

Figure 3. 3D Printer Use Training.

The STEAM methodology for learning development is based on the successful experience of the STEM-FabLab Classroom in Manizales, adapted to the particularities and needs of each campus. Key aspects such as strategic planning, resource identification, specialized personnel selection, and acquisition of equipment and technologies are addressed. The development of the STEAM Classrooms promotes technological development and skills training in the cities of Bogotá, Medellín, and Tumaco, strengthening the innovation ecosystem and creating opportunities for the personal and professional growth of the participants. Project-based methodology and knowledge transfer are expected to impact the university community positively. The goals of this process are:

- Application of technological solutions that improve quality of life and promote local progress.
- Comprehensive training of professionals in STEAM areas.
- Promoting employability.
- Entrepreneurship in the business sector.
- Strengthening the innovation ecosystem.
- Generating development opportunities.
- Social transformation.

3.2 Enhancing STEAM Learning with Neurodidactic Principles

The relationship between the inter-campus STEAM classrooms at the National University of Colombia (UNAL) reflects a teaching and learning methodology that addresses the specific needs of diverse communities and territories. A central aspect of this methodology is the integration of neurodidactics, which leverages principles of neuroscience to optimize learning processes in STEAM disciplines. This approach has proven to have a significant impact on how students acquire and process knowledge. Below, several key strategies are outlined:

Personalization of Learning: By employing neurodidactics, UNAL educators can identify and respond to students' differences and needs across various knowledge domains. This enables the design and implementation of strategies, activities, and projects tailored to diverse learning styles, enhancing the educational experience in STEAM spaces.

Enhancement of Retention and Comprehension: Neurodidactic principles emphasize the importance of emotion and motivation in learning. In STEAM classrooms, where concepts can be particularly complex and challenging, applying techniques that create emotional connections with the study material can significantly improve content retention and understanding.

Development of Critical and Creative Thinking Skills: Neurodidactics promotes methods that stimulate critical and creative thinking, which are essential in STEAM. Students can develop these crucial skills through practical problem-solving and interdisciplinary group projects, driving innovation and creative problem-solving.

Encouragement of Curiosity and Exploration: Applying neurodidactic principles in STEAM teaching helps design lessons that foster exploration and curiosity. This is particularly valuable in fields such as science and engineering, where discovery is key to learning.

Integration of Learning Technologies: Neurodidactics also guides the integration of emerging technologies in the classroom, such as virtual reality, simulations, and interactive platforms. These tools can make abstract concepts more tangible and accessible to students.

Implementing these practices in UNAL's STEAM classrooms improves the quality and effectiveness of learning. It prepares students to tackle future challenges in their fields innovatively and adaptively.

3.3 Learning Areas and Lines

Each learning line aims at one or more areas worked on in STEAM so that all classroom members, regardless of their career, can develop new skills that nourish interdisciplinarity and thus create synergy between all fields of action. This allows projects to be built and strengthened from different angles, utilizing insights from neurodidactics to enhance cognitive engagement and emotional connectivity with the content, ensuring that learning processes are effective and retained over time.

- **Extended Realities:** Explore and experiment with virtual, augmented, and mixed reality technologies. Learn to develop immersive applications and content, applying design, programming, and digital narrative concepts. Neurodidactic strategies maximize sensory and experiential learning, facilitating more profound understanding and memory retention.

- Internet of Things (IoT): Students delve into connected devices and machine-to-machine communication. Learn to design and program IoT solutions, implementing sensors, actuators, and simulation platforms. The curriculum incorporates principles of neuroeducation to enhance problem-solving and critical thinking, which are essential for innovating in IoT.
- Machine Learning: Participants discover the fundamentals and applications of machine learning. Explore algorithms, data analysis techniques, predictive model development, and their application in different contexts and issues. Lessons are designed to align with cognitive patterns that foster analytical thinking and comprehension, supported by neurodidactic approaches.
- Programming: Students develop programming skills in Python, JavaScript, C++, and more. They learn to design and build applications and technological underpinnings, applying good programming practices and problem-solving. Neurodidactics structure learning sequences that progressively build on existing knowledge, enhancing logical reasoning and coding efficacy.
- Electronics and Circuits: This learning line delves into electronics and circuits, from understanding essential components to building and programming electronic circuits. Participants acquire skills in circuit design, soldering, and laboratory tools. Teaching methods are adapted to foster hands-on learning and spatial reasoning, which are critical in electronics, through neurodidactic principles.
- 3D Modeling: This area delves into three-dimensional modeling using specialized software. Learn to create and modify objects in virtual environments, applying design and rendering techniques for prototyping and projects. The pedagogical approach leverages visual and spatial learning strategies derived from neurodidactics, enhancing mental visualization and manipulation of objects.
- Architecture and Design: This course explores the fundamentals of architecture and design, focusing on applying innovative technologies and methodologies. Participants learn to create functional spaces and objects, considering aesthetics, ergonomics, and sustainability. Neurodidactics informs the integration of sensory experiences in design education, facilitating a deeper understanding of the interplay between form, function, and environmental impact.

Figure 4. STEAM Event in Bogotá to contextualize classroom work.

4 Results

4.1 Development of Training Processes

A series of virtual training sessions via YouTube was conducted to ensure effective knowledge transmission, activate motivation, and ensure adequate learning processes. These sessions, led by experts in each topic, covered various emerging technologies. The sessions were divided into theory and practical exercises, providing a comprehensive learning experience. Prior to these sessions, all participants voluntarily registered, confirming their consent to use the data to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the training.

Initially, student interest was attracted through the presentation of innovative and successful projects that have taken place in the STEM Classroom at the UNAL Manizales campus. This allowed students to observe the scope of their ideas and how they can scale up to become viable and marketable products.

Subsequently, agile methodologies and soft skills were addressed as pillars for time management, faster project completion, and the use of digital tools necessary for task management. With these foundational training sessions, an introduction to more specific topics was given, such as:

- Entrepreneurship and innovation in STEAM addressed the necessary steps to start a successful business.
- Design and sustainability-focused on using renewable energies to produce electricity in hard-to-reach areas.
- Technologies for digital transformation, directed towards data science, formulated a simple project that included using Python and a database to relate similar concepts and provide conclusions.
- Extended realities cover the types of realities (real reality, augmented reality, virtual reality, mixed reality), their operations, and a step-by-step example of approaching the use of Unity as a development engine to generate applications focused on these topics.
- Design and artificial intelligence focused on using AI to facilitate and expedite the creation of graphic pieces, their advantages and disadvantages, possible advances, and risks.
- Intellectual property in project management, the proper registration of projects, the difference between intellectual property and patents, the problems that AI produces in these cases, and the types of innovation.
- Sensory and industrial processes: This section explains the types of sensors used for factory monitoring, provides examples of use, and includes a practical exercise carried out online.

Figure 5. Training "Deepening of projects based on emerging technologies.

For these training sessions, a previous voluntary registration of 1200 people from all campuses of the National University of Colombia was made, of which a total of 3465 views were achieved and a session rating of 314 people. Several strategies were implemented to assess and enhance the participants' learning experience. At the end of each session, a satisfaction survey was conducted to gather feedback and perceptions on the effectiveness of the training. Additionally, questions and concerns from participants were actively addressed during the sessions, ensuring dynamic interaction and continuous support.

To measure the knowledge acquired more objectively, interactive Kahoot quizzes were used. These quizzes, conducted at the end of each session, allowed for the assessment of information retention and provided immediate feedback to both instructors and students on the concepts learned.

Furthermore, step-by-step follow-along exercises were incorporated to foster a practical and deep understanding of the topics covered. These exercises were designed for participants to apply what they had learned in practical situations, thus strengthening their familiarity and proficiency with the discussed tools and concepts. These evaluative and participatory activities increased interaction during the sessions. They provided valuable data for continuous improvement of the content and teaching methods, ensuring that the learning objectives were effectively met.

Figure 6. Raining qualification statistics

5 Discussion

The National University of Colombia training sessions are designed to leverage neurodidactic principles to optimize learning environments and enhance cognitive engagement. This approach aligns with the principles of neuroscience that focus on how the brain learns, ensuring that teaching methods are not only effective but also resonate with the brain's natural learning processes. The data presented in the bar chart provides an insightful evaluation of how these principles impacted the outcomes.

5.1 Analysis of Survey Results

Level of Interest in the Topics Addressed: High ratings in 'Excellent' reflect significant enthusiasm and cognitive engagement, essential components in neurodidactic strategies. A high level of interest is crucial as it is associated with increased neural activity in brain regions related to attention and memory, enhancing the overall learning experience.

Quality of Knowledge Required: The feedback ranging from 'Satisfactory' to 'Excellent' suggests that the sessions successfully met cognitive expectations and were well-tailored to the participants' levels of understanding. This aligns with neurodidactic practices that emphasize aligning educational content with the learners' cognitive development stages and prior knowledge.

Contribution to Skill or Knowledge Enhancement: Predominantly, 'Excellent' ratings in this category indicate that the sessions highly strengthened neural connections related to the skills and concepts discussed. This effectiveness is a core goal of neurodidactic approaches, which aim to facilitate durable learning and retention by engaging multiple neural pathways.

5.2 Impact of Neurodidactic Strategies

Interactive quizzes on Kahoot and structured follow-along exercises are practical applications of neurodidactic theories. These tools not only actively engage learners but also provide immediate feedback, which is known to reinforce neural pathways and facilitate the consolidation of new knowledge. The quizzes assess information retention and adjust teaching tactics in real-time, while the exercises promote the application of knowledge, ensuring deeper neural encoding and retrieval pathways.

5.3 Participant Interaction and Neuroplasticity

Addressing participants' questions and concerns during the sessions contributed to creating a responsive learning environment that adapts to the learners' needs, another key aspect of neurodidactic teaching. This adaptive learning environment supports neuroplasticity, the brain's ability to reorganize itself by forming new neural connections in response to learning.

6 Conclusion

Adopting pedagogical approaches based on a deep understanding of brain functioning during learning has designed more effective and meaningful teaching experiences. This commitment to neuroeducation allows for addressing students' cognitive and emotional needs, optimizing information retention, and promoting critical skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving.

The STEAM methodology, in turn, has been implemented through interdisciplinary projects that connect science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics, providing authentic and applicable learning contexts. This approach improves student interest and participation and prepares them for the complex challenges of the real world, thus promoting comprehensive and applied education. These methods have made the learning process more enjoyable and engaging and enhanced the cognitive and emotional resonance of the content, which are critical for deep and lasting learning. The results affirm that applying neurodidactic principles in STEAM education can significantly enhance the immediate understanding and the long-term retention of complex concepts, fulfilling the strategic educational goals of the National University of Colombia.

The UNAL STEAM Classrooms are a clear example of how integrating these methodologies can transform the educational environment. They provide a space for experimentation, research, and the development of innovative technological solutions. These classrooms represent a step forward in STEAM education, allowing students to learn in a theoretical context and apply their knowledge in practical projects that reflect current and future challenges.

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